

Adaptive Intrusion Detection in IoT Networks via Transformer-Based Learning and Dynamic Feature Optimization

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Abstract

Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS) play a critical role in safeguarding modern network infrastructures against increasingly complex cyber attacks. However, traditional machine learning methods frequently struggle when the data has many features and they require a lot of manual work to select which features are important. To counter this type of problem, our study presented a hybrid deep learning framework and compared three different approaches such as A Baseline CNN-LSTM Attention model with an enhanced CNN -Transformer Encoder Model and a Dynamic Binary Particle Swarm Optimization(PSO) based model for feature selection. This approach uses the NSL-KDD dataset to test the models on different features. The data is prepared using normalization techniques for feature scaling and one-hot encoding to represent categorical attributes numerically. These models were trained such as the first one was baseline hybrid deep learning model, second is Transformer Encoder model, which captures to detect long range dependencies in the data and the third one is PSO Optimized model which works by selecting the most important features to reduce the size of data. The experimental findings revealed that the CNN Transformer Encoder model achieved the best detection performance by reaching the highest accuracy and F1 scores because it can capture relationships across the entire dataset. On the other hand, Dynamic PSO reduces the number of features while maintaining performance. This approach indicates that Transformer Encoder with self attention mechanism and PSO Optimization techniques produce a more robust and efficient IDS for wireless Internet of Things (IoT). The source code used in this study is publicly available at: <https://github.com/hassaan145/adaptive-iot-intrusion-detection.git>.

Keywords: Intrusion Detection, CNN, Transformer Encoder, Dynamic (PSO), NSL-KDD, Wireless Internet of Things (IoT)

1. Introduction

1.1. Background

Wireless Internet of Things Sensor Networks (WIoTSNs) are rapidly expanding and are reshaping the development of contemporary systems, ranging from smart healthcare and agriculture to industrial environments [14]. As these networks scale, they produce substantial volumes of sensitive data, making data security and privacy a critical concern [15]. Although these networks have insufficient battery power and processing speed and they are usually placed in wild areas which makes them simple targets for hackers [13]. Recent studies indicate the need for fast, precise, and effective deep learning methods to ensure efficient protection of such networks [1]. Therefore, a robust and automated security mechanism is required to keep these connected devices working properly. The main approaches to protect these networks can be broadly categorized into two types: Traditional Hybrid models and modern attention based models [16].

1.2. Related Work

Early research efforts integrated tools like Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM)

to develop security systems [7]. Hybrid models offer the advantage of effectively capturing temporal patterns, thereby outperforming static learning approaches. However, a significant drawback was their tendency to lose information when processing extensive data stream. As a result, they frequently failed to identify complex attacks especially those hidden within power limited IoT devices [10].

Attention-Based Models: To encounter the memory problem, recent studies have been using Transformer Encoder models [4]. They read the data in step by step, unlike older models. Transformers employ a self-attention mechanism that enables the model to analyze the entire input context simultaneously [29]. Research by Zhang et al [2] and Liu and Wu [3] demonstrated that self attention technique helps the system to focus on most important details, hence it finds the hidden attack patterns that older models failed to recognize.

Identified Gaps: Besides many improvements, some important gaps still remain. Current models still fail to correctly label many different types of attacks [4]. Furthermore, they are slow and become very heavy on small battery operated IoT devices [5]. This justifies the need for a new finding that is both accurate and efficient to find the complex errors along with preserving battery power.

1.3. Problem Statement

Even with the improvements, current models still face the difficulty to spot smart complex attacks [3]. Older models like LSTM often struggle to retain long sequences of data and complex attacks [21]. Also these systems can not classify different types of attacks occurring at once. For instance, research illustrates that standard model often struggle to sort different attack types accurately [4]. While some models identify learning what is normal, they work well on limited IoT devices without consuming enough power, is now a big challenge [5].

1.4. Contributions

To solve the above mentioned problems, our research suggested a strong security framework that uses a "Transformer Encoder" combined with PSO method. We have used "Self Attention Technique" and "Dynamic Particle Swarm Optimization" algorithm (used to select the most important data features by ignoring the noise).

Our work has the following main contributions:

1. We implemented a CNN Transformer Encoder model to detect the complex attacks.
2. We used Dynamic PSO that reduced the amount of data without affecting accuracy.
3. We compared the base paper method with our new methods. This study suggested an important and scalable security solution for the next generation of wireless sensor networks.

2. Methodology

This section provided a detailed research design, preparation of datasets, algorithms and experiments to evaluate the proposed intrusion detection system (IDS).

This study comprises of these Deep Learning Architectures:

2.1. Dataset and Preprocessing

Here the newer version of KDD'99 benchmark which is Network Security Laboratory Knowledge Discovery Dataset (NSL-KDD) dataset has been used to solve the duplication of the original dataset [18]. This dataset contained 125,973 training records and 22,544 testing records. Every record has 41 features which were divided into basic, content, and traffic based features. Each record is labeled as either normal traffic or an attack. Data preprocessing was performed to match coherence with deep learning models. First, symbols were converted into numerals using One Hot Encoding [11]. It elaborated the features from 41 to 119 dimensions. In addition, Normalization of the Z score [12] was applied to normalize the range of independent variables using

$$z = \frac{x - \mu}{\sigma}$$

where x is the original feature value, μ is the mean of the feature vector, and σ is the standard deviation.

2.2. Model Architectures

Three different model architectures were used and developed to evaluate the attention mechanism and feature selection.

2.2.1. Model A: Baseline CNN-LSTM-Attention

The base paper model was developed to represent the current state of the hybrid approach [9]. It adopted Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) with 128 filters and kernel size of 3 to evaluate the features. It observed Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) with 64 units to catch temporary packages.

Figure 1: Baseline CNN-LSTM-Attention Architecture

2.2.2. Model B: CNN Transformer Encoder

To reduce processing limitations of LSTMs, the second model was replaced with Transformer Encoder. This architecture used a multi-head self attention mechanism [29, 25], which is used to weigh the relevance of different parts of input sequence. The Transformer consists of 3 encoder layers with 8 attention heads and network dimensions of 512.

2.2.3. Model C: Dynamic PSO-Optimized Framework

The third model used a Dynamic Binary Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) algorithm [26, 27] to perform feature selection. This optimization aimed to reduce the high dimensionality of the dataset by selecting only the most relevant features.

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PSO initial best: 0.9706928303803899
Iter 5/100 best=0.9707
Iter 10/100 best=0.9707
Iter 15/100 best=0.9707
Iter 20/100 best=0.9721
Iter 25/100 best=0.9721
Iter 30/100 best=0.9721
Iter 35/100 best=0.9721
Iter 40/100 best=0.9721
Iter 45/100 best=0.9721
Iter 50/100 best=0.9721
Iter 55/100 best=0.9721
Iter 60/100 best=0.9721
Iter 65/100 best=0.9721
Iter 70/100 best=0.9721
Iter 75/100 best=0.9721
Iter 80/100 best=0.9721
Iter 85/100 best=0.9721
Iter 90/100 best=0.9721
Iter 95/100 best=0.9721
Iter 100/100 best=0.9721
Selected features: 57
Using device: cuda

```

Figure 2: CNN Transformer Encoder Architecture

2.3. Experimental Setup and Parameters

All experiments were conducted in a cloud-based computational environment using Google Colab. The hardware specifications included an NVIDIA T4 Graphics Processing Unit (GPU) with 16 GB Video Random Access Memory (VRAM) and 12 GB of system RAM. The algorithms were implemented using Python 3.10, utilizing the TensorFlow and Keras libraries for deep learning model construction and the Scikit-learn library for data preprocessing and evaluation metrics. All the models passed through a standard training to make sure the comparison is fair and maintainable. The Adam optimizer was employed for gradient descent. For the CNN-LSTM and PSO-based models, a learning rate of 0.001 was used with a batch size of 64. The Transformer model utilized a learning rate of 0.0005 with a batch size of 128 to accommodate its higher parameter complexity. All models were trained for 50 epochs, with the Dynamic PSO algorithm running for 100 iterations with a population of 24 particles.

3. Results

3.1. Performance Comparison

Model	Accuracy (%)	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	F1-Score (%)
CNN	75.18	92.09	61.69	73.89
LSTM	76.89	92.26	64.84	76.16
CNN-LSTM	75.27	91.85	62.05	74.07
CNN-LSTM + Attention	73.86	91.74	59.43	72.13
CNN Transformer Encoder	75.83	92.08	62.96	74.79
Dynamic PSO + CNN-LSTM	79.09	88.00	70.00	78.00

Table 1: Performance comparison of baseline and improved intrusion detection models

The models were assessed using Accuracy, Precision, Recall, and F1-Score, with results in Table 1. Standalone LSTM and CNN models had similar performance, with accuracies of 76.89 percentage and 75.18 percentage. The CNN-LSTM model achieved 75.27 percentage, while adding Attention dropped it to 73.86 percentage. The CNN Transformer Encoder model reached 75.83 percentage accuracy. The Dynamic PSO + CNN LSTM model performed best, achieving an accuracy of 79.09%, along with strong recall and F1-scores.

3.2. Feature Optimization Analysis

The impact of the Dynamic Binary PSO algorithm on feature dimensionality and computational efficiency is detailed in Table 1. The algorithm successfully reduced the feature space from the original 119 features (after one-hot encoding) to 57 selected features. This approximate 52% reduction in input dimensionality contributed to the observed performance improvement by removing noisy attributes while retaining key discriminative features.

3.3. Classification Analysis and Visualizations

To further evaluate the more detailed classification, ROC curves and confusion matrix were designed. Figure 3 indicates the comparison of Transformer model with the Reference model. The Transformer model retains a true positive rate upto 1.0 which is low false positive rate, which also shows its resilience in separation of normal traffic and attack traffic. (FPR)[3, 2].

Figure 3: Classification Analysis of ROC Curve

In (Figure 4) specific class separation has been presented by Confusion matrix. Whereas the reference model encounters challenges with the false negatives, but the Transformer design effectively addressed these challenges like uncertainties which results in 75.80% of F1 scores.

Figure 4: Confusion matrix analysis

4. Discussion

4.1. Interpretation of Findings

It is clear in (Figure 6) that CNN Transformer Encoder Model indicates exceptional performance from the Baseline and PSO-Optimized CNN-LSTM models for sure. The considerable increase in accuracy upto 75.83% is a result of Multi Head Self Attention Mechanism, which also helps the model to identify global patterns across different features. By comparison to LSTM which processes data step by step and is more prone to information loss in long sequences because of vanishing gradients, here Transformers execute all the information synchronously, which also facilitates the identification of sophisticated and scattered intrusion behaviours. On the other hand in (Figure 5), Dynamic PSO model (79.09%) ensures that there is a presence of duplicated and noisy features in NSL-KDD dataset. The computational overhead decreased by model and it improved generalization, even though minimum than the improvement after integrating Transformer Architecture. This was achieved by eliminating 52% of unnecessary features. In Figure 7 an analysis of accuracy and F1 score further supports these findings and in Figure 8 illustrates the difference in performance between the CNN-LSTM Attention Model and the Dynamic PSO Variant.

Figure 6: Accuracy comparison across Epochs (CNN+Transformer and CNN+LSTM)

Figure 7: Accuracy and F1-Score comparison of BASE vs IMPROVED

Figure 5: Accuracy Comparison (Dynamic PSO vs Base) across Epochs

Figure 8: Bar Comparison: CNN-LSTM + Attention vs Dynamic PSO

4.2. Comparison with Literature

These findings reinforce with recent research literature. According to Liu and Wu [3], our paper suggests that Attention based mechanism is a more robust approach for detection of anomaly

compared to traditional iterative models. Although, Zhang et al [2] proposed Hybrid Transformer BiLSTM model. Our research suggests that standalone Transformer Encoder model is best to achieve highest accuracy and it is also better in simplification of the Architecture. In addition, the partial success of PSO model addresses the challenges of efficiency by Abdulameer's [5] which ensures that adaptive algorithms are needed for resource constraint in which minimizing the model size is more important than achieving highest accuracy.

4.3. Implications

This study indicates a visible trade off for WIoTSN security implementations. In critical environments, where security consistency is essential, hence Transformer Model is best choice because of its highest accuracy in detection mechanism. Although for peripheral devices with strict battery, an equitable solution has been offered by PSO Optimized model which also provides reduced computational cost while surpassing standard baseline performance.

5. Conclusion

This Research is focused to improve Intrusion Detection System in Wireless IoT Sensor Networks by reducing the limitations of Traditional CNN-LSTM models. We have effectively designed, developed and tested two improvements: first is CNN Transformer Encoder Model and the second is Dynamic PSO Feature Optimized Architecture. The primary results demonstrate that Transformer Encoder model obtained a significant accuracy of 75.83% which outperforms the Reference model which has the accuracy of 73.86%. The Dynamic PSO Optimized feature selection model competently minimized dimensions of features by 52% without trade off to performance predicted. These improvements bridges the gap that self attention mechanisms are important to detect complicated attacks while growing optimization algorithms are essential to improve performance in resource limited environments. Further research will emphasize on integrating lightweight variants of Transformer Encoder Models on physical devices like Tiny BERT to access real time energy utilization and transmission delay in real time network environments.

6. References

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